

PROPERTIES OF ACTIVATED SUGAR CHARCOAL
COATED WITH VARIOUS ORGANIC SUBSTANCES.
PART III. CATALYTIC DECOMPOSITION OF
HYDROGEN PEROXIDE.

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Influence of coats of palmitic acid and α -naphthylamine on activated sugar charcoal on the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide has been studied. Both the coats are equally active and increase the catalytic decomposition of hydrogen peroxide irrespective of acidity or alkalinity of the coats.

In a previous paper (Acharya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 198) the adsorptive properties of activated sugar charcoal, coated with various acidic and alkaline substances, have been reported. In this paper the effect of such coats on the catalytic decomposition of hydrogen peroxide has been studied at 32°.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The charcoal used in the following experiment was obtained by activating pure sugar charcoal at 800° for 6 hours.

The coats of palmitic acid and of α -naphthylamine were produced by the method already described (*loc. cit.*). Coats were produced so as to contain 0.01 g. of the substance per g. of charcoal. About 92 to 93% of the coat can be recovered by Soxhlet extraction with alcohol.

To each of 50 c.c. portions of hydrogen peroxide solution (about 3% contained in a cleansed Jena glass bottle 0.5 g. of the following adsorbents were added :

- (i) Activated charcoal,
- (ii) Palmitic acid coated charcoal, and
- (iii) α -Naphthylamine coated charcoal.

A control was also kept. The concentration of hydrogen peroxide was determined by titration against standard potassium permanganate solution and has been given in g. per 100 g. of solution.

R E S U L T S.

TABLE I.

	Control.	Activated charcoal.	Palmitic acid coated charcoal.	<i>a</i> -Naphthylamine coated charcoal.
Initial conc.	2'72	2'72	2'72	2'72
Final conc.				
(i) after 2 hrs.	2'72	2'58	2'49	2'51
(ii) after 24 hrs.	2'72	2'15	1'74	1'80
Millimoles decomposed per g. of charcoal				
(i) after 2 hrs.	—	4'00	6'70	6'20
(ii) after 24 hrs.	—	16'00	28'00	26'50

TABLE II.

	Control.	Activated charcoal.	Palmitic acid coated charcoal.	<i>a</i> -Naphthylamine coated charcoal.
Initial conc.	2'82	2'82	2'82	2'82
Final conc.				
after 2 hrs.	2'82	2'73	2'68	2'70
24	2'82	2'41	1'97	1'07
48	2'77	2'18	1'40	1'40
72	2'77	1'72	0'85	0'86
Millimoles decomposed per g. of charcoal				
after 2 hrs.	—	2'50	4'00	3'30
24	—	12'50	24'00	24'00
48	—	20'20	40'2	40'20
72	—	31'00	56'5	56'00

The following results were obtained using 1 g. of charcoal.

TABLE III.

	Control.	Activated charcoal.	Palmitic acid coated charcoal.
Initial conc.	3.09	3.09	3.09
Final conc.			
after 20 hrs.	3'00	2'43	2'11
40	3'07	1'85	1'19
72	1'04	1'46	1'01
Millimoles decomposed per g. of charcoal			
after 20 hrs.	—	19'30	28'8
40	—	35'70	55'0
72	—	57'00	70'2

D I S C U S S I O N .

Tables I, II and III show that both palmitic acid and α -naphthylamine considerably promote the decomposition of H_2O_2 solution by sugar charcoal to the same extent (Table II, curves 1, 2). The promoting effect is greater in dilute solutions and rises during the reaction to a maximum and then diminishes. The decomposition increases with the amount of charcoal employed. The p_H values of conductivity water kept in contact with charcoal coated with palmitic acid and α -naphthylamine for 24 hours are 5.19 and 6.46 respectively (Acharya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 723). The fact that both coats have the same effect in spite of the difference in p_H shows that their acidity or alkalinity is of little significance.

Curves 1 and 3 refer to activated charcoal; curves 2 and 4 refer to charcoal coated with palmitic acid or with α -naphthylamine.

In curves 3 and 4, $\log C$ has been plotted against time t where C is the concentration of H_2O_2 at time t kept in contact with the charcoal. The straight line curves indicate that the decomposition of H_2O_2 by activated charcoal and coated charcoal follows a unimolecular reaction rate. But the unimolecular velocity constant k gradually diminishes with time in case of both activated and coated charcoal. Similar diminutions in the values of

k which ultimately become exceedingly small were obtained by Firth and Watson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 125, 1750, *cf.* Kepfer and Walton, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 557) with sugar charcoal. Coated charcoals behave exactly similarly as activated charcoals without coat (Curves 1, 2, 3 and 4). It has been pointed out before that the decomposition increases with the amount of charcoal. It appears therefore that the promoting effect is mainly due to the increase in active surface (*cf.* Acharya, *loc. cit.*).

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